

Anatoxins in cyanobacterial mat field samples from Atlantic Canada by direct analysis in Real Time–High Resolution Tandem Mass Spectrometry

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Abstract

Toxic freshwater benthic cyanobacterial mats are increasingly linked to animal fatalities worldwide, often due to the production of high concentrations of anatoxins (ATXs). Considering the high spatial and temporal variability of mat occurrence and concentrations of ATXs, suitable analytical methods are required to enable large-scale field studies in these systems. Here, a rapid, direct analysis in real time–high resolution tandem mass spectrometry (DART–HRMS/MS) method for analysis of anatoxin-a, homoanatoxin-a, and dihydroanatoxin-a including a simple sample preparation procedure and isotope dilution calibration, is investigated to address this challenge. The developed method was applied to three sets of cyanobacterial mat samples collected in Atlantic Canada in the summers of 2018–2020. Samples from all sets showed positive detection of ATXs ranging from $<100 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ to $> 70,000 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ in mat lysates. One large mat sample collected from the Wolastoq (Saint John River) in New Brunswick, Canada, was used to demonstrate the application of DART–HRMS/MS to study the intra-mat variability of ATXs. This initial work showed the method could be successfully used for the analysis of ATXs in field samples, which will be useful in ongoing studies of this emerging issue in Atlantic Canada and beyond.

Keywords: Cyanotoxins, *Phormidium*, *Microcoleus*, ambient ionization

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Introduction

Proliferations of freshwater benthic microbial mats dominated by cyanobacteria of the genera *Microcoleus*, *Phormidium*, and *Oscillatoria* are increasingly being reported globally (McAllister *et al.*, 2016; Wood *et al.*, 2020) and are often associated with pet and livestock mortalities (Stevens and Krieger, 1988; Backer *et al.*, 2013; Faassen *et al.*, 2012; Fastner *et al.*, 2018). In the majority of cases, these mortalities can be attributed to poisoning by the potent alkaloid neurotoxin anatoxin-a (ATX) and its structural analogues, collectively referred to as anatoxins (ATXs; Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of anatoxins analyzed in this study.

Challenges associated with studying these proliferations of toxic benthic cyanobacteria include the extremely high spatial and temporal variability in mat occurrence and ATX concentrations within a study area (Wood *et al.*, 2012, 2020). These challenges could be better addressed with analytical methods capable of providing higher throughput analysis as well as improved selectivity and sensitivity over existing approaches.

Direct analysis in real time (DART) is an ambient ionization technique that is capable of vaporizing and ionizing certain analytes for mass spectrometry (MS) detection without the need for a chromatographic separation

(Gross, 2014). This technique is particularly powerful when combined with high-resolution MS (HRMS), which helps improve selectivity in the absence of chromatographic separation. DART-MS has been widely used for the analysis of pesticides, mycotoxins, and drugs of abuse (Busman, 2018; Gross, 2014). Analysis of ATXs by DART was recently demonstrated for screening laboratory cultured cyanobacterial isolates (Beach *et al.*, 2021) but its applicability to more complex field samples has not yet been explored.

Here, we present initial work on a DART-HRMS/MS method for analyzing ATXs in benthic cyanobacterial mat samples. We then demonstrate the utility of the method using cyanobacterial mat samples from Atlantic Canada.

Material and Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

A certified reference material calibration solution for ATX and an in-house calibration solution for homoanatoxin-a (hATX) were obtained from the National Research Council Canada (Halifax, Nova Scotia). Standards of $^{13}\text{C}_4$ -(+)-Anatoxin-a and dihydroanatoxin-a (H_2 -ATX) were obtained from Eurofins Abraxis (Warminster, U.S.A.).

Samples and Sample Preparation

Three cyanobacterial mat samples from three sample sets were collected from Atlantic Canada between 2018 and 2020. Sample set 1 (NS 2019-1 to -3) included suspected cyanobacterial mats collected from brackish waters near Oak Island, Nova Scotia (44.5123° N, 64.2949° W),

in September 2019. Sample sets 2 and 3 consisted of *Microcoleus*-dominated benthic cyanobacterial mats collected along the Wolastoq (Saint John River) near Fredericton, New Brunswick (45.9636° N, 66.6431° W) during the summers. Sample set 2 (NB 2019-1 to -4) was collected in July 2019 following a nearby dog mortality.

Samples were homogenized and stored at -20 °C prior to analysis. Sub-samples of homogenate (~1 mL) were centrifuged at 21,000 × g at 4 °C for 20 min. A sub-sample of supernatant (100 µL) was then mixed with 100 µL of 120 ng mL⁻¹ ¹³C₄-ATX in 90% methanol with 0.015% acetic acid.

DART-HRMS/MS Analysis

A Q Exactive HF Orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo, Waltham, MA, U.S.A.) was coupled to a DART-SVP source using a Vapur® interface (Ionsense, Saugus, MA, U.S.A.). Helium was used as the DART gas along with a DART temperature of 350 °C, a capillary temperature of 200 °C and Max IT of 300 ms. Mass spectrometric data were collected simultaneously in full scan over the mass range of 150 to 250 *m/z* and precursor ions of *m/z* 166.1 (ATX), 168.1 (H₂-ATX), 180.1 (hATX), and 170.1 (¹³C₄-ATX) were isolated for tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) using the parallel reaction monitoring scan mode with a collision energy of 15 eV, a 0.4 *m/z* isolation window and the 30k resolution setting. Product ions extracted for quantitation were *m/z* 149.0961, 163.1117, 125.0961, and 153.1095, for ATX, hATX, H₂-ATX, and ¹³C₄-ATX, respectively.

Samples were introduced by pipetting five µL of extract onto the tip of a Dip-it sampling rod and manually holding the sample mid-way

between the DART source and the ceramic interface tube for 10 s (Fig. 2). All samples were analyzed in triplicate and a mixed standard (43 ng mL⁻¹ ATX, 46 ng mL⁻¹ hATX, 37 ng mL⁻¹ H₂-ATX and 60 ng mL⁻¹ ¹³C₄-ATX) was run approximately every 10 samples.

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of manual Dip-it sample introduction used for DART-HRMS/MS.

Results and Discussion

The full scan DART-HRMS method recently presented for the analysis of ATXs in laboratory cultured cyanobacteria (Beach *et al.*, 2021) was not suitably selective for use with more complex benthic cyanobacterial mat field samples. A tandem mass spectrometry (HRMS/MS) method was therefore developed that showed improved selectivity but maintained good sensitivity. Figure 3 shows extracted ion chromatograms from analysis of benthic cyanobacterial mat samples collected in 2019 from the Wolastoq. All samples and the mixed ATX standard were spiked with 60 ng mL⁻¹ ¹³C₄-ATX. Comparing the signal intensity of ¹³C₄-ATX in figure 3 effectively demonstrates the significant and variable degree to which ionization suppression was observed in field samples, up to > 99% suppression. Though significant, this suppression was successfully corrected for by isotope dilution calibration, allowing for quantitation of ATXs by DART-HRMS/MS.

Fig. 3. Extracted ion chromatograms from DART-HRMS/MS showing triplicate analysis of a mixed ATX standard and four benthic cyanobacterial mat samples collected from the Wolastoq in 2019.

Quantitative results from three sets of benthic cyanobacterial mats analyzed by DART-HRMS/MS are shown in Table 1. Sample set 1 consisted of suspected cyanobacterial mats collected from brackish waters near Oak Island, NS in Sept 2019. In this case, low levels of H₂-ATX and hATX were detected in one sample, but the other two were below the limits of detection, which were estimated at 5 ng mL⁻¹ lysate based on 3× the background in control mat extracts. These findings were later confirmed using an LC-HRMS method with a limit of detection of 0.1 ng mL⁻¹ (method as in Beach *et al.* (2021), data not shown).

Light microscopy revealed cyanobacterial cells consistent with the *Microcoleus/Phormidium/Oscillatoria* complex in all three samples (Fig. 4), further supporting the

Fig. 4. Light micrographs of two morphotypes of filamentous cyanobacterial cells observed at 400× magnification in samples from Oak Island, Nova Scotia. Panel A) major morphotype, and panel B) minor one.

results of toxin analysis by DART-HRMS/MS. Two morphotypes of cyanobacteria were present. The dominant morphotype (Fig. 4A) was significantly larger in size with a trichome width roughly 1.5× larger than the other morphotype (Fig. 4B) and with thicker cross walls.

Sample set 2 was collected in July 2019 from the shore of the Wolastoq, where an ATX-associated dog death had occurred three days prior. These samples showed variably high concentrations of ATXs consistent with previously reported dog mortalities elsewhere in the world (Backer *et al.*, 2013; Faassen *et al.*, 2012; Fastner *et al.*, 2018). End-point PCR targeting the *anaC* gene, one of the genes involved in anatoxin biosynthesis, confirmed the presence of *anaC* in all samples (method as in Rantala-Ylinen *et al.* (2011), data not shown).

Table 1. Concentrations of ATXs as measured by DART–HRMS in benthic cyanobacterial mat samples from Atlantic Canada.

Sample	ng toxin mL ⁻¹ lysate			
	ATX	hATX	H ₂ -ATX	Total
set 1				
NS 2019-1	87	0	9	96
NS 2019-2	0	0	0	0
NS 2019-3	0	0	0	0
set 2				
NB 2019-1	15060	414	4183	19657
NB 2019-2	2737	128	153	3018
NB 2019-3	9740	121	2569	12431
NB 2019-4	45142	192	15673	61007
set 3				
NB 2018-1	78	4	38	119
NB 2019-5	1111	44	13883	15038
NB 2019-6	30829	181	43430	74440
NB 2019-7	55	6	109	169
NB 2020-1	295	2	320	618
NB 2020-2	107	0	5	113
NB 2020-3	288	2	206	495
NB 2020-4	826	12	42	879

Samples from set 3 were collected from the Wolastoq throughout the summers of 2018–2020 and analyzed to study the broader inter- and intra-mat variability of ATXs in the system. All samples were positive for ATXs, with total ATX concentrations varying by nearly three orders of magnitude.

Sample NB 2018-1 was a large (400 g wet) mat sample that was further sub-sampled in order to demonstrate the capabilities of DART–HRMS in studying small-scale variability of ATXs within a mat (Fig. 5). H₂-ATX concentrations varied by over

an order of magnitude within the sample, however, overall variability was relatively low compared with what has been reported previously (Wood *et al.*, 2012). It should be noted that the sample had been previously frozen, partially thawed, and re-frozen prior to sub-sampling. Considering freeze-thaw is a generally accepted means of cyanobacterial cell lysis, it is expected that the results shown in figure 5 may be an under-estimate of actual intra-mat variability in ATX concentrations.

Fig. 5. Concentrations of ATXs measured by DART–HRMS/MS (A) from sub-sampled locations (B) of frozen benthic cyanobacterial mat NB 2018-1.

The work summarized here demonstrates that DART methodology, originally developed for screening culture samples (Beach *et al.*, 2021), could be refined using HRMS/MS detection to be suitable for application to more complex field samples. The method was applied to show the presence of ATXs in samples from Atlantic Canada, with an initial demonstration of the utility of the method for evaluating inter- and intra-mat variability. Work is ongoing to optimize and validate

the DART method parameters for field work and to apply the method in a broader study of cyanobacterial mat and ATX occurrence in the Wolastoq. The method is equally applicable to work in other areas with widespread or suspected proliferations of toxic benthic cyanobacteria. In the future, the throughput of the method could be further improved through automation of sample introduction.

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